

THE T.Z.H & PILLAR METHOD:

The little-linker

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* image courtesy Desmos*

$$\begin{aligned} \text{In integration, the area will be } \int_0^x x^2 &= \frac{x^{2+1}}{2+1} - \frac{0^{2+1}}{2+1} \\ &= \frac{x^3}{3} \end{aligned}$$

But we can also do this using my T.Z.H ,

Think that the area of the curve is covered with rectangles which are 0 unit wide, so the wide of pillar = 0

& the number of those pillars will be $n = \frac{x}{0} = A(x)$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Now with the formula } \sum_{k=0}^n k^2 &= \frac{n(n+1)(2n+1)}{6} \text{ the total (h)} = \frac{A(x)(A(x)+1)(2A(x)+1)}{6} \\ &= \frac{A(x)^2 \times 2 \times A(x)}{6} \\ &= A\left(\frac{x^3}{3}\right) \end{aligned}$$

So the total area will be : wide \times h

$$\begin{aligned} &= 0 \times A\left(\frac{x^3}{3}\right) \\ &= \frac{x^3}{3} \end{aligned}$$

Even here area according to the integration , $\int_0^x x^n dx = \frac{x^{n+1}}{n+1}$

in this case the number of those pillars will be $(x) = A(x)$

According to the **Faulhaber's Formula**, the total (h) = $\frac{x^{n+1}}{n+1} = \frac{A(x)^{n+1}}{n+1} = A\left(\frac{x^{n+1}}{n+1}\right)$

$$\begin{aligned} \therefore \text{ area : } &0 \times A\left(\frac{x^{n+1}}{n+1}\right) \\ &= \frac{x^{n+1}}{n+1} \end{aligned}$$

Now triangle,

T.Z.H, The wide of pillar = 0

The number of pillar = $A(x)$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Using arithmetic progression, the total height (h)} &= \frac{A(x)\{A(x)+1\}}{2} \\ &= \frac{A(x) \times A(x)}{2} \quad [\because A(x) \pm y = A(x)] \\ &= \frac{A(x)^2}{2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Area} = 0 \times \frac{A(x)^2}{2} = \frac{x^2}{2}$$

Now circle,

Circle's radius = r

So the perimeter = $2\pi r$

Now split the circle into like a pie chart. And the triangle two sides' length is = r

And other is = 0

According to my T.Z.H, we will have $\frac{2\pi r}{0}$ triangle = $A(2\pi r)$ triangle

So the area of the circle = those triangles' total area = $A(2\pi r) \times \frac{1}{2} \times 0 \times \sqrt{r^2 - \frac{0^2}{2^2}}$

$$= A(2\pi r) \times 0\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) \times \sqrt{r^2}$$

$$= A(2\pi r^2) \times 0\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)$$

$$= 2\pi r^2 \times \frac{1}{2}$$

$$= \pi r^2$$

Now sphere,

radius = r

So imagine cutting the sphere into tiny pyramids whose base is 0

So we will get $A(4\pi r^2)$. Now for a pyramid the area will be $0\left(\frac{r}{3}\right)$

So the total volume is $A(4\pi r^2) \times 0\left(\frac{r}{3}\right)$

$$= \frac{4}{3}\pi r^3$$